

Enhancing Anammox Performance in Wastewater Treatment: The Role of Type of Granular Activated Carbon

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Abstract

Removal of nitrogenous compounds from wastewater is crucial to prevent ecological stress, stimulation of eutrophication, and biodiversity loss. Anaerobic ammonium oxidation (anammox) has emerged as an alternative, cost-effective, and sustainable technology to conventional nitrification-denitrification methods. However, anammox systems are sensitive to environmental factors, with challenges such as prolonged start-up times and organic carbon inhibition limiting their efficiency. This study aims to comprehensively evaluate the role of granular activated carbon (GAC) type, steam activated and chemically activated carbon, in enhancing the performance and stability of anammox reactors in the presence of organic matter. By addressing the aforementioned challenges, the research also seeks to determine whether GAC can improve the resilience of anammox systems. Overall results revealed that GAC addition extended the acclimation period from an average of 18.5 ± 3.5 days (control) to 43 days but significantly enhanced nitrogen removal efficiency. Upon introducing organic carbon, total nitrogen removal efficiency in Control 2 (reactor without GAC + with organic matter) dropped to 34.90%. In contrast, GAC-containing systems maintained high performance (PK1-3: $94.96 \pm 3.46\%$; Norit-C: $94.68 \pm 4.05\%$). These findings demonstrate that GAC mitigates organic carbon inhibition and stabilizes anammox activity, highlighting its potential to optimize nitrogen removal in wastewater treatment systems. Experiments are ongoing as part of the study. It is aimed to observe system resistance to higher organic carbon concentrations as well as to evaluate the extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) response of the enriched anammox culture and track the changes in microbial composition.

Keywords

Anammox; biological nitrogen removal; granular activated carbon; organic carbon; start-up period

INTRODUCTION

Nitrogen compounds in wastewater are key indicators of water quality and must be effectively removed to prevent eutrophication and its associated ecological impacts. Traditional nitrification-denitrification processes have been widely employed to convert ammonium (NH_4^+) into nitrogen gas (N_2) (Can *et al.* 2021). However, the discovery of the anaerobic ammonium oxidation (anammox) process in the 1990s (Jetten *et al.* 1998) revolutionized nitrogen removal due to its cost-effectiveness, low sludge production, energy efficiency, and reduced carbon footprint (Trinh *et al.* 2021). Anammox involves the anoxic oxidation of NH_4^+ with nitrite (NO_2^-) as the electron acceptor, producing N_2 . Despite its advantages, the process is highly sensitive to environmental factors, such as pH (optimal range: 6.7-8.3), temperature (30-40°C) and nitrogen loading, which can significantly impact anammox activity and the process efficiency (Cho *et al.* 2020). One of the key challenges of anammox processes is the extended start-up period, resulting from the slow growth rate. These prolonged start-up durations may delay the efficient implementation of treatment systems, increase operational costs, and pose barriers to large-scale applications (Lin *et al.* 2023). The anammox process also faces limitations due to the adverse effects of high organic carbon, such as acetate, concentrations existed in wastewaters (Cho *et al.* 2020). Additionally, activated carbon (AC), particularly granular activated carbon (GAC), is widely utilized in drinking water and wastewater treatment due to its ability to adsorb organic pollutants and its economic feasibility (Campinas *et al.* 2022; Phillips *et al.* 2022). Incorporating AC in anammox reactors may mitigate the inhibitory effects of organic carbon by adsorbing excess organic compounds, potentially improving bacterial

activity and process stability.

Considering these aspects, this study investigates the effects of activation method (steam activation and chemical activation) two different types of activated carbon, namely PK1-3 and Norit-C, on anammox performance. To achieve this, this study was performed in two stages. In the first stage, activated carbon was added to anammox bioreactors to evaluate their influence on start-up periods of anammox bioreactors. Subsequently, organic carbon (sodium acetate, CH₃COONa) was introduced to the reactors, with applied concentrations gradually increased to analyse its impact on anammox activity in systems containing activated carbon. Overall, findings aim to elucidate strategies for optimizing anammox-based nitrogen removal processes in wastewater treatment, addressing challenges related to organic carbon inhibition and improving reactor performance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Prior to conducting experiments, four sequential batch reactors with a working volume of 500 mL were established. Seed sludge from a six-month operational enrichment reactor was equally distributed among the reactors. Two reactors were designated as controls, while PK 1-3 and Norit-C GAC types were added to the other two at 15 g each. Norit C, a wood-based granular activated carbon, features a highly open pore structure consisting of meso and macro pores. It is manufactured through chemical activation with phosphoric acid. Norit PK 1-3, on the other hand, is a coal-based granular activated carbon produced via heat activation and mainly a microporous activated carbon. Reactors were maintained at $35 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ in an incubator. To create an anoxic environment for anammox bacteria, mixed gas of N₂/CO₂ (95/5%) was continuously introduced into the systems, and freshly prepared feeds were purged with 100% N₂ gas before feeding. The detailed feed composition has been previously reported in the literature (Can *et al.* 2021). Hydraulic retention time of the bioreactors was adjusted to 2 days. All analytical analyses (NH₄⁺-N, NO₂⁻-N and COD) were conducted according to Standard Methods (APHA 1998). Once steady-state nitrogen removal performance was observed and nitrogen removal efficiency exceeded 85% in all bioreactors, sodium acetate was added as an organic carbon source in a total of 3 bioreactors, 2 of which contained GAC. The last reactor has been continuing to operate as a control bioreactor. The initial concentration of CH₃COONa was set at 40 mg/L COD and was subsequently increased. The experimental period in this study was divided into different phases, as explained in detail in Table 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During start-up, the total operating time of the bioreactors was 143 days. Results demonstrated significant differences in the time required for reactors to reach steady-state conditions. Reactors without GAC stabilized in an average of 18.5 ± 3.5 days, while GAC-containing reactors required at least 43 days, indicating that GAC addition prolongs the acclimation period of the anammox systems (Table 2). However, despite the extended acclimation time, GAC addition enhanced anammox activity in synthetic wastewater treatment compared to control groups.

Table 1. Details of experimental period (phases by days) and organic carbon addition to the bioreactors (mg/L COD).

	Phase 0 (Start-up) (days 0-143)	Phase I (days 144-170)	Phase II (days 171-191)	Phase III (days 192-continue)
Control 1	-	-	-	-
Control 2	-	40	60	80
PK1-3	-	40	60	80
Norit-C	-	40	60	80

Table 2. The impacts of different types of granular activated sludges on the nitrogen removal performance of anammox cultures in Phase 0.

	NH ₄ ⁺ -N R.E. in Phase 0, %	NO ₂ ⁻ -N R.E. in Phase 0, %	Time to reach SS, days	NH ₄ ⁺ -N R.E. after SS, %	NO ₂ ⁻ -N R.E. after SS, %
Control 1	87.46	80.60	15	90.06	83.11
Control 2	84.11	77.73	22	86.58	77.73
PK1-3	85.78	81.40	51	94.56	91.94
Norit-C	93.73	90.56	43	96.54	93.74

R.E.: Removal Efficiency; SS: Steady State

Before the application of organic carbon to the anammox systems, total nitrogen (sum of NH₄⁺-N and NO₂⁻-N) removal efficiencies of both control reactors were found to be 85.66 ± 8.01% after steady state. During the same period, the total nitrogen treatment performance of the anammox bioreactors containing GAC also increased to 94.76 ± 5.38% (Figure 1). On day 144, CH₃COONa was introduced to Control 2, PK1-3 and Norit-C systems (Table 1). Control 1 continued to operate as an essential control bioreactor during the experiments. Once organic carbon was added to the Control 2 reactor, which did not contain activated carbon, nitrogen removal performance decreased rapidly to 34.90% as the applied concentration increased (Figure 1). However, regardless of the type, nitrogen removal performance in systems containing GAC (PK1-3 or Norit-C) has not been negatively affected as in the Control 2 reactor. In the same period, the total nitrogen removal performance in the reactor with PK1-3 was 94.96 ± 3.46%, while the removal performance in the reactor with Norit-C was determined as 94.68 ± 4.05%, which are also very close to the results of the Control 1 reactor (92.48 ± 7.66%) (Figure 1). It is possible that the irreversible adsorption of sodium acetate onto the interior surfaces of GAC rendered it inaccessible to the anammox bacteria, effectively shielding them from inhibition.

Figure 1. Nitrogen removal performance of anammox bioreactors throughout the operation.

Experiments are currently underway as part of the study. Moving forward, as the organic carbon concentrations in the reactors continue to be increased in a stepwise manner, the variations in adsorption and desorption profiles of the activated carbons—related to their activation methods—could significantly influence the availability of organic carbon. Reactor operations will continue until the resistance of anammox systems containing active carbon to inhibition is fully assessed. Additionally, the extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) response of the microbial population will

be monitored throughout the reactor operation period, and changes in microbial composition will be analysed in detail using next-generation sequencing.

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REFERENCES

- APHA 1998 *Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater*. American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association, Water Environmental Federation, Washington, D.C.
- Campinas M., Viegas R. M. C., Almeida C. M. M., Martins A., Silva C., Mesquita E., Coelho M. R., Silva S., Cardoso V. V., Benoliel M. J. & Rosa M. J. 2022 Powdered activated carbon full-scale addition to the activated sludge reactor of a municipal wastewater treatment plant: Pharmaceutical compounds control and overall impact on the process. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, **49**, 102975.
- Can S., Sari T. & Akgul D. 2021 Recovery profile of anaerobic ammonium oxidation (anammox) bacteria inhibited by ZnO nanoparticles. *Water Science and Technology*, **85**(1), 342-353.
- Cho S., Kambey C. & Nguyen V. K. 2020 Performance of Anammox Processes for Wastewater Treatment: A Critical Review on Effects of Operational Conditions and Environmental Stresses. *Water*, **12**(1).
- Jetten M. S. M., Strous M., van de Pas-Schoonen K. T., Schalk J., van Dongen U. G. J. M., van de Graaf A. A., Logemann S., Muyzer G., van Loosdrecht M. C. M. & Kuenen J. G. 1998 The anaerobic oxidation of ammonium. *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*, **22**(5), 421-437.
- Lin L., Zhang Y. & Li Y.-Y. 2023 Enhancing start-up strategies for anammox granular sludge systems: A review. *Science of the Total Environment*, **902**, 166398.
- Phillips B. M., Fuller L. B. M., Siegler K., Deng X. & Tjeerdema R. S. 2022 Treating Agricultural Runoff with a Mobile Carbon Filtration Unit. *Archives of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, **82**(4), 455-466.
- Trinh H. P., Lee S.-H., Jeong G., Yoon H. & Park H.-D. 2021 Recent developments of the mainstream anammox processes: Challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, **9**(4), 105583.